

Motion sickness comparison of 2 XR approaches: camera+screen or hologram on transparent lens (Meta Quest 3 or Microsoft HoloLens 2)

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Abstract—With the growth of technical capabilities of virtual reality headsets, more headsets are receiving XR mode using cameras to display the surrounding world (Apple Vision Pro, Meta Quest 3, VIVE XR Elite). These headsets are positioned as a full-fledged alternative to headsets with hologram on transparent lens, such as Microsoft HoloLens 2. Meanwhile, one of the reasons holding back the rapid rise in popularity of XR is the motion sickness that occurs when using VR/XR headsets. In this study, we experimented to determine which of the two approaches (camera+screen or hologram on transparent lens) has less motion sickness and which solution can be considered more promising for XR exploration in the future. As a result, our research shows that hologram on transparent lens has much less motion sickness in the current stage of technical progress. Still, its issues need to be solved to provide a non-motion sickness experience to the user.

Index Terms—Extended Reality, Motion Sickness, Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Digital Twin

I. INTRODUCTION

Virtual Reality (VR) and Extended Reality (XR) technologies have witnessed unprecedented advancements in recent years, fueled by innovations in hardware capabilities and immersive content creation. These technologies hold promise across diverse domains, ranging from entertainment and gaming to education [1], healthcare [2], and industrial applications [3]. With the emergence of XR headsets featuring camera-based XR modes, such as the Apple Vision Pro, Meta Quest 3, and VIVE XR Elite, a new frontier of immersive experiences has unfolded, offering users the ability to blend virtual and real-world environments seamlessly.

In parallel, traditional XR devices utilizing holographic displays on transparent lenses, exemplified by the Microsoft HoloLens 2, have set a benchmark for mixed-reality experiences. These devices overlay holographic content onto the

user's field of view, enabling interactions with digital elements while maintaining spatial awareness of the physical surroundings. As the XR landscape evolves, the choice between XR and holographic displays on transparent lenses has become a subject of considerable debate, with implications for user experience, application versatility, and technological feasibility.

Despite the promise of XR technologies, a notable obstacle persists: Virtual reality sickness, also known as VR motion sickness [4], which refers to the physical discomfort experienced when the brain receives conflicting signals regarding self-movement within a digital environment. The mismatch between visual stimuli presented by the headset and the user's physical motion and discrepancy between the sensory signals received by the brain from the eyes and inner ear within the XR environment can induce discomfort, dizziness, and nausea, undermining the immersive potential of XR experiences [5].

Addressing motion sickness is vital to realizing the full potential of XR technology and facilitating its widespread adoption across various domains. Many research efforts have been dedicated to comprehending and alleviating the impacts of motion sickness in VR environments and have shed light on various factors contributing to motion sickness in VR/XR, these factors include age, gender, and the user's previous experience of motion sickness experiences [4], [6], [7], but none of these researches studied the XR technique used by the headset to display the content (i.e. camera+screen or hologram on the transparent lens) as a factor for VR motion sickness.

In this work, we aim to conduct an empirical study to analyze and compare the effect of XR display approach used in headsets on the motion sickness of the users, specifically, we compare the motion sickness between headsets that use camera-based XR (Meta Quest 3) versus those employing holographic displays on transparent lenses (Microsoft HoloLens

2). During the experiment, each user tried the same VR environment app in the two types of headsets, and the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ) [8] was used after each try to assess symptoms of simulator sickness in the user such as headache and dizziness.

II. BACKGROUND

In this section, we'll provide fundamental background information covering the causes of VR motion sickness, factors influencing susceptibility to it, and strategies for minimizing its occurrence. This foundational knowledge is crucial for gaining insights into how XR technology impacts motion sickness in VR/XR settings.

A. VR motion sickness causes

Research indicates that several factors contribute to VR motion sickness. Firstly, hardware-related factors [4] such as display mode and visual delay latency play a significant role. Additionally, the narrow field of view offered by many VR headsets has been associated with feelings of claustrophobia and disorientation. Secondly, content-related factors [9], including fast-moving graphics and disorienting scenarios, can heighten the risk of motion sickness. Examples of such scenarios include sudden changes in altitude or speed, as well as unexpected collisions with virtual objects. Lastly, individual physiological differences [7], classified under human factors, can influence susceptibility to VR motion sickness. Prolonged use of VR headsets may also lead to symptoms such as eye strain, headaches, and fatigue, further increasing the likelihood of experiencing motion sickness.

B. Susceptibility to VR motion sickness

VR motion sickness can affect individuals of any age or gender who use a VR/XR headset. While the risk is universal, certain groups may be more prone to experiencing disorientation and nausea. Children and young adolescents, especially those under the age of 13, are particularly vulnerable due to ongoing maturation and development of their vestibular systems [6]. Some studies suggest that women may be more susceptible to VR motion sickness compared to men, although conclusive evidence is lacking [9]. Additionally, individuals who regularly experience motion sickness, such as during travel, are likely to be more susceptible to VR/XR-induced discomfort, regardless of age or gender [10]. During our study, we did not conduct testing on children, and before starting the test, we recorded the presence of a natural predisposition to seasickness.

C. VR motion sickness minimization

VR motion sickness poses a significant challenge to the widespread adoption of VR/XR technologies. However, developers and end users can employ various strategies to mitigate its effects. One approach involves adjusting the default frame rate, with developers focusing on increasing the speed at which each frame refreshes to at least 72 FPS to minimize lag time and image shaking. Additionally, investing in improved

hardware performance, particularly hardware that integrates features to reduce latency [11], can help alleviate sensory conflicts. For instance, minimizing the lag time between a user's physical actions and the corresponding shifts in the virtual environment can reduce discrepancies between visual and sensory feedback. Other hardware solutions include using headsets positioned further from the user's face and exploring mixed reality options to provide a fixed horizon or visual reference point. Furthermore, thorough testing of each VR experience, particularly with individuals sensitive to frame rates, can help developers ensure that their content is smooth and free from elements that could induce motion sickness. By implementing these measures, developers and end users can work together to create VR experiences that are more comfortable and accessible to a wider audience.

Users can take proactive measures to minimize the likelihood of experiencing VR motion sickness. Starting with manageable sessions and gradually increasing duration allows users to acclimate to the virtual environment, with breaks taken immediately upon noticing any symptoms of discomfort. Adjusting VR settings to lower graphics quality and decrease movement speed and acceleration can also help alleviate symptoms. Staying hydrated by drinking water and avoiding large or spicy meals before VR sessions is advisable. Additionally, opting to sit rather than stand during VR experiences reduces the risk of motion sickness, with users encouraged to use a stable, rotating chair securely anchored to the floor for added comfort and stability. By adopting these strategies, individual users can enhance their VR experiences and reduce the occurrence of motion sickness.

III. RELATED WORK

The distribution of VR/XR headsets to users and the constant increase in the number of devices in this category have led to an increase in the number of research related to VR/XR. One of the areas of research development is studying the issue of motion sickness that may occur in headset users. Some scientific works consider the general problem of motion sickness when using VR/XR headsets [4], [12]. Numerous studies have shed light on various factors contributing to VR/XR-induced motion sickness. These factors encompass a wide range of variables, including gender disparities, the genre of virtual environments, characteristics of VR/XR experiences, graphical fidelity, illuminance levels within virtual environments, and individuals' prior experiences with motion sickness. Gender differences have been identified as potential influencers, with some research indicating a higher susceptibility among women [9]. Furthermore, the genre of virtual environments, such as gaming versus educational simulations, may influence the likelihood of experiencing motion sickness [10]. The intensity and nature of VR/XR experiences play a pivotal role; highly dynamic or visually stimulating experiences are more likely to induce motion sickness [13]. Additionally, graphical properties like frame rate and resolution have been scrutinized for their impact on user comfort and well-being in VR settings [7], [14]. Lighting conditions within virtual environments, charac-

Fig. 1: Interface of our XR demo (same for both devices)

Fig. 2: Interaction between user and real world using our XR demo

terized by illuminance levels and the presence of flickering lights, have also emerged as significant contributors to motion sickness [15].

Furthermore, individuals with prior experiences of motion sickness, whether in VR/XR or other contexts, exhibit varying degrees of susceptibility, suggesting a potential link between past encounters and future responses. Additionally, research has delved into the physiological ramifications of motion sickness in VR/XR, revealing correlations with heart rate, blood pressure, and blood sugar levels [16], [17].

Understanding the intricate interplay between these factors and motion sickness is crucial for developing effective strategies to alleviate discomfort and enhance user experience in VR/XR environments [14]. This body of research underscores the multidimensional nature of motion sickness in VR/XR and highlights the imperative for continued investigation and intervention to foster safer and more inclusive VR/XR experiences.

Most studies try to detect the dependence of motion sickness on specific parameters of the user or the content consumed by the user. Our study is the first study in the field of XR, which investigates the impact on the appearance of motion sickness from different technologies that create a XR environment for the user.

IV. EXPERIMENTS SETUP

In this section, we will detail the setup of the experiment by describing the devices (headsets) we used, the group of participants, the evaluation questionnaire, the task that participants will do during the experiment using the VR headsets, and the implementation procedure.

A. Hardware

For our experiments, we used Meta Quest 3 and Microsoft HoloLens 2 to test motion sickness in headsets that use a camera-based approach and holographic displays on transparent lenses approach respectively. The Meta Quest 3 comes with

a Qualcomm Snapdragon XR2 Gen 2 CPU, 8GB RAM, and a display with a 110-degree field of view with 120 HZ refresh rate and 1440x936 resolution for each eye. While Microsoft HoloLens 2 has Qualcomm Snapdragon 850 CPU, 2GB RAM, and a display with a 50-degree field of view with 75 HZ refresh rate and 1440x936 resolution for each eye. Before the test, the two headsets were adjusted to fit the participant, this included adjusting the straps that fix it on the head for comfortable use and maximum picture clarity and calibrating the display to the user's eyes.

B. Participants

For a comprehensive outcome, a group of 24 participants was studied, the group was designed to cover different ages, genders, wearing/not wearing glasses, and previous experience in using VR. The studied group consisted of 12 female and 12 male participants, average age is 30 years (standard deviation: 4.2 years) with no physical or visual health problems. All the participants were from Technische Universität Dresden (Germany) and recruited through a university's intranet. 21 of these participants normally use medical glasses in their daily lives, during the experiments they removed the glasses, and the headset displays were tuned so they had no visual difficulties performing the VR tasks without the glasses. Among all participants, 6 had previous experience in using VR, and 3 owned a VR device. Thus, this was an experimental group with little experience using VR. We explained to all participants the details of the experiment which included: *i*) the questionnaire is anonymous, *ii*) the experiment will last approximately 30 minutes, *iii*) the purpose of the experiment is to measure motion sickness, therefore, the participants can take a rest whenever they want to, and *iv*) participants can stop the experiment freely when they feel severe motion sickness.

C. Tasks

Our study simulates the active use of XR to assess the current state of the technology for the possibility of mass use during full-time work or everyday life. All participants were tasked with performing identical tasks one time wearing two different headsets. These tasks involved movements such as walking and looking around, during which the users encountered virtual objects integrated into the real environment. Fig. 1 illustrates the interface of the environment observed by the users during these tasks. The sequence of activities included the following steps: Upon wearing and adjusting the headset in a room, participants were required to open a door while visually focusing on their hand as shown in Fig. 2, thereby observing their hand interacting with a real object within the XR environment. Subsequently, participants exited the room and closed the door, simulating real-world interactions through the XR experience. During this action, participants altered their body orientation multiple times. Following this, participants were instructed to walk briskly and comfortably to the end of a 45-meter corridor and then return. Throughout this movement, the visual imagery continuously changed for the participants, potentially intensifying sensations of motion sickness due to any disparity between visual perception and cognitive processing. Finally, participants had to open the door to re-enter the room in the same manner, enter, and close the door behind them, all while maintaining visual focus on their hand interacting with the door.

D. Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate motion sickness during the experiments, we used the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ) [8] which is a widely used tool for assessing symptoms of simulator sickness, including those induced by virtual reality (VR) environments. Developed by Kennedy, Lane, Berbaum, and Lilienthal in 1993, the SSQ aims to quantify the severity of symptoms experienced by individuals exposed to simulators, such as flight or driving simulators, as well as VR systems. As shown in detailed Table I, the SSQ comprises 16 questions that evaluate various symptoms commonly associated with motion sickness, such as nausea, disorientation, eyestrain, and headaches. Participants are asked to rate how strongly they experience each symptom on a scale ranging from 0 (no symptoms) to 3 (severe symptoms), thus offering a detailed index of their total discomfort. The collected responses are then utilized to compute the scores for each symptom category, following the equations presented in Table II.

E. Implementation

We prepared a demonstration ¹ with optimized frame rates and avoided rapid image transitions, conducting preliminary tests to ensure the software’s compatibility and eliminate any potential for inducing motion sickness. The experiment was structured to limit user sessions to a maximum of 5 minutes and avoided XR testing immediately after meals, reflecting

¹(<https://bitbucket.org/tu-dresden/motion-sickness/>)

SSQ items	Nausea	Oculomotor	Disorientation
1. General discomfort	0	0	
2. Fatigue		0	
3. Headache		0	
4. Eyestrain		0	
5. Difficulty focusing		0	0
6. Increased salivation	0		
7. Sweating	0		
8. Nausea	0		0
9. Difficulty concentrating	0	0	
10. Fullness of head			0
11. Blurred vision		0	0
12. Dizzy (eyes open)			0
13. Dizzy (eyes closed)			0
14. Vertigo			0
15. Stomach awareness	0		
16. Burping	0		
Total	[1]	[2]	[3]

TABLE I: Symptoms in SSQ.

SSQ components	Computation
Nausea	[1]×9.54
Oculomotor	[2]×7.58
Disorientation	[3]×13.92
Total	([1]+[2]+[3])×3.74

TABLE II: Computation of SSQ scores.

XR’s intended use in dynamic everyday scenarios. Testing also involved active motion to align with XR’s purpose of aiding users in real-world activities, distinct from stationary VR experiences. To prevent carryover effects, the second headset was tested only after confirming the absence of negative sensations from the previous test. After each session, participants were asked to fill out the detailed SSQ questionnaire, which aimed to gauge the severity of any motion sickness they may have experienced. This questionnaire utilized a simple 4-point scale, allowing participants to express the degree to which they felt unwell. Furthermore, after the experiment, we conducted thorough debriefing sessions with each participant to gain deeper insights into their individual experiences and any potential areas of concern. All participants engaged in identical tasks while wearing two different headsets, with experiment durations ranging from 10 to 35 minutes, inclusive of breaks, to facilitate recovery from motion sickness. The variable duration allowed participants to individually gauge their readiness for subsequent experiments, ensuring optimal conditions for assessment.

V. EVALUATION RESULTS

Our objective is to investigate the variance in motion sickness experienced by users when using different XR techniques

Fig. 3: SSQ results for Microsoft HoloLens 2, Meta Quest 3

Fig. 4: SSQ results for Microsoft HoloLens 2, Meta Quest 3

(camera+screen or hologram on transparent lens) that are typically used in virtual reality (VR) headsets.

The SSQ scores in Fig. 3 revealed significantly higher motion sickness symptoms for users of the Meta Quest 3 compared to the Microsoft HoloLens 2. This trend was consistent across all SSQ subscales, including nausea, oculomotor discomfort, disorientation, and total score. Specifically, the mean SSQ scores for Meta Quest 3 were substantially higher than those for Microsoft HoloLens 2 in the following categories: nausea (27.83 vs. 6.36), oculomotor discomfort (39.16 vs. 10.74), disorientation (45.24 vs. 12.76), and total score (42.39 vs. 11.22).

A closer examination of the SSQ results Fig. 4 for each device shows specific symptoms that users experienced. Users of Microsoft HoloLens 2 reported the highest levels of general

discomfort, Eyestrain, blurred vision, and dizziness (eyes closed). Conversely, none of the participants using HoloLens 2 reported increased salivation, nausea, vertigo, stomach awareness, or burping.

Following the SSQ assessment, we engaged in detailed discussions with each participant to delve into their individual experiences. Through rigorous analysis of the gathered data, several insights emerged. Regarding Meta Quest 3, participants highlighted significant issues relating to image quality. Despite advancements in VR/XR headset technology, the current hardware solution fails to deliver imagery on par with reality, significantly trailing behind the holographic approach implemented in Microsoft HoloLens 2.

Moreover, participants expressed concerns about delays experienced while using Meta Quest 3, particularly during active movement. This delay, attributed to the transmission lag between cameras and screens, amplifies discomfort for users. On the other hand, while Microsoft HoloLens 2 offers advantages such as enhanced freedom of movement, it introduces its own set of challenges. Notably, the device's susceptibility to shaking during motion detracts from the user experience. Additionally, prolonged usage of HoloLens 2 leads to eye fatigue, primarily due to the complex lens system necessary for projecting virtual elements on transparent glass. This limitation contrasts with the seamless clarity typically associated with standard vision correction glasses, prompting negative user sentiments after just a few minutes of use.

In summary, both implementations of XR technology in the current generation of headsets tend to induce motion sickness when used in motion. However, utilizing holographic projection on transparent lenses appears to evoke fewer adverse effects compared to employing displays and cameras. All participants reported experiencing motion sickness after using Meta Quest 3, with most also experiencing discomfort with Microsoft HoloLens 2. This suggests that neither technology is currently suitable for daily use. Nevertheless, all study participants experienced motion sickness during active use of XR mode on these devices. Currently, VR headsets can be comfortably used in XR mode when the user remains stationary or engages in short periods of activity.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

With each new generation of XR headsets, helmets become lighter, more mobile and have significantly better technical characteristics. Headset manufacturers have several technological steps left before the XR device can become the new phone that we will use as the main means of communication. At the current time, our research shows that XR technology cannot be fully used on a daily basis due to the discomfort it creates for the user.

Currently, XR occupies a niche of convenient setup of a VR headset or in most cases is used for specific, narrowly focused tasks in production without the need for a large number of movements in space. It is motion sickness that is one of the biggest factors that limits the mobile possibilities of using XR and slows down the development of the entire industry.

Having two completely different approaches to the implementation of the XR experience allows you to solve the problem of motion sickness in different ways. Our research identifies and describes the main challenges of each of the XR technologies that hinder the diffusion of XR into people's daily lives.

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